

Synthesis, Characterization and Antimicrobial Activity of Fe(II) and Mn(II) Complexes with Schiff base derived from naphthaldehyde and p-chloroaniline

Na'aliya J.

Department of pure and Industrial Chemistry, Bayero University, Kano. Nigeria

Ibrahim A. K.¹

Department of pure and Industrial Chemistry, Bayero University, Kano. Nigeria

Email: al.ameen91@yahoo.com

Sadiq A. I.

Department of pure and Industrial Chemistry, Bayero University, Kano. Nigeria

Sambo B. U.

Department of chemistry Federal University, Gusau Nigeria

Haruna A.

Department of chemistry Federal University, Gusau Nigeria

Abstract: The Schiff base derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and p-chloroaniline and its Fe(II) and Mn(II) complexes were synthesized and characterized using infrared spectral analysis, melting point/decomposition temperature, magnetic susceptibility, conductivity measurement, solubility test, and elemental analysis. The Schiff base and its metal complexes were screened for antimicrobial activity. The molar conductance values range ($3.54 - 5.83 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) indicated all complexes are nonelectrolytes. The magnetic susceptibility values revealed that all the complexes are paramagnetic. The infrared spectra analysis suggested that the Schiff base behaves as a bidentate ligand coordinates to metal ion via azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen. The high decomposition temperature range ($201 - 223^\circ \text{C}$) revealed the stability of the complexes. The elemental analysis results revealed slight differences between observed and calculated percentages of C, H, and N in the Schiff base and its metal complexes, this is in line with their proposed structures, and also revealed a 1:2 metal-ligand ratio in all the complexes. The antimicrobial activity of the Schiff base and its complexes were conducted using the agar well diffusion method against two bacteria strains; (*Salmonella typhi* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*) and two fungal isolates; (*Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Rhizopus species*). The results revealed that the Schiff base and its metal complexes exhibited promising antimicrobial activity.

Keywords: Schiff base; Complexes; 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde; p-chloroaniline; Antimicrobial activity.

Introduction:

¹Corresponding author

The Schiff bases are characterized by the presence of the azomethine functional group (-C=N-) and are usually formed by condensation of a carbonyl compound (aldehyde or Ketone) with a primary amine (Iniama and Isaac, 2013). The first reports of this kind of reaction have been published by Hugo Schiff in the 1860s. Thereafter the Schiff bases have been intensively used as synthetic intermediates and as Ligands for coordinating transition and inner transition metal ions, (Anita et al., 2010). Schiff base Ligands may contain a variety of substituents with different electron-donating or electron-withdrawing groups, and therefore may have different interesting chemical properties. Schiff bases have been widely used as ligand because of the high stability of their coordination compounds, good solubility in common solvents such as methanol, chloroform, Dimethylsulfoxide and Dimethylformamide e.t.c (Bharat *et al.*, 2015), relevant biological application, high flexibility, and medicinal efficacy (Jai, *et al.*, 2016). Schiff bases obtained from aromatic aldehyde and aromatic amines have shown a number of applications in many fields such as pharmaceutical, life sciences, and chemical science (Muzammil *et al.*, 2015). These important compounds have been reported to possess diverse biological activities such as antifungal, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antioxidant, and antitumor (Neelofar *et al.*, 2017).

Metal complexes have been receiving considerable attention for many years, due to their interesting characteristics in the field of material science and a biological system (Rajendra, *et al.*, 2012). Metal complexes have an important application in medicinal chemistry. Medical science demands such types of compounds that are more potent, biologically active, easily absorbable and nontoxic, and show fast action for the treatment of diseases (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2017).

Extensive studies revealed that chelation makes the complex more stable and biologically more active in the presence of bio-metal. Metal ions fixed the complexes at the specific active site of the proteins and enzymes of the host and show their potentiality (Chaudhary, 2013).

Experimental Materials and Methods:

All chemicals were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and used without further purification. All glassware used was washed with detergent after soaking in conc. HNO₃, rinsed with distilled water and dried in an oven. The weighing was conducted using the electrical Melter balance model AB54. Infrared spectral analysis was determined using Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (FTIR-8400S) range 4000-400cm⁻¹. Electrical conductance was measured using the Jenway conductivity meter model 4010 range 20-200μs. Melting points and decomposition temperatures were determined using the microprocessor melting point apparatus (WRS-IB). Magnetic susceptibility was determined using magnetic susceptibility balance MKI Sherwood scientific ltd. Elemental analyses were determined using Series II CHNS/O 2400, Perkin Elmer.

Preparation of Schiff base:

The Schiff base was prepared by mixing the ethanolic solution of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthadehyde with that of ethanolic solution of p-chloroaniline in a 1:1 ratio. The resulting solution was refluxed for 4 hours and then cools to room temperature; on cooling the precipitate formed which was filtered, washed, and recrystallize with ethanol and diethyl-ether and then dried in desiccators over anhydrous CaCl₂ for 72hrs (Gomathi, *et al.*, 2013).

Scheme1: Preparation of Schiff Base

Preparation metal complexes:

The complexes were prepared by mixing a hot ethanolic solution of hydrated metal chloride salts with that of hot ethanolic solution of Schiff base ligand in 1:2 ratios. The resulting mixture was reflux for 8 hours, in each case, and then cool to room temperature, on cooling the precipitate formed, which was filtered, washed with ethanol and diethyl-ether several times to remove any excess ligand. And finally dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 in desiccators to obtained the required complex (Gomathi, *et al.*, 2013). The hydrated metal chloride salts include; Fe(II) and Mn(II) salts respectively.

Scheme 2: Preparation of Complexes

Determination of Melting point of Schiff base and Decomposition Temperature of the metal complexes:

The melting point of the Schiff base and the decomposition temperature of metal complexes were determined using the microprocessor melting point apparatus (WRS-IB). The obtained are shown in Table 1 (Aliyu and Ado 2010).

Solubility Test:

The solubility test of Schiff base and its metal complexes were carried out in water, ethanol, methanol, acetone, and chloroform, Dimethylsulfoxide, Dimethylformamide and

Diethyl-ether in which 0.2g of each sample was tested in 10ml of each solvent. The results obtained are shown in Table 2 (Yusuf *et al.*, 2018).

Determination of Water of Hydration in the Complexes:

0.2g of prepared complex each was placed in a clean weighted Petri dish which was then placed in an oven at 110 °C for 72 hours, until a constant weight was obtained.

The weight loss if any, recorded as the water of hydration from the constant weight of anhydrous complex; the percentage water of hydration was calculated for each complex using the expression below (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2017).

$$\% \text{ water of hydration} = \frac{\text{weight loss}}{\text{initial weight of sample}} \times 100\%$$

Molar conductance measurements:

1mmol of each complex was dissolved in 10ml of Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and the corresponding specific conductance value was recorded using Jenway conductivity meter model 4010. (Moamens, 2013)

From the specific conductance value recorded, the molar conductance of each metal complex was calculated using the expression below. The results obtained are shown in Table 4.

$$\text{Molar conductance} = \frac{100 \times \text{specific conductance}}{\text{ionic concentration}}$$

Magnetic Susceptibility Measurement:

The magnetic susceptibility of complexes was determined using magnetic susceptibility balance MKI Sherwood science ltd via the expression below. The results obtained are shown in Table 5 (Javed, 2006).

$$X_g = CL \frac{(R - R_0)}{10^9 M}$$

Where X_g = Mass susceptibility, $C = 1$ (Constant), L = Sample length in the tube (whose range should be set between 1.5 to 3.5cm, R = Reading obtained from the sample packed in the tube, R_0 = Reading obtained from preweight empty tube, M = mass of the sample in the tube (measured in gram).

Antimicrobial activity:

The synthesized Schiff base and its metal complexes were screened antimicrobial activity against two pathogenic bacteria strains i.e. (*Salmonella typhi* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*) and two fungal isolates; i.e. (*Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Rhizopus species*) by the agar well diffusion method. The wells (6 mm in diameter) were dug in the media with the help of a sterile metallic borer. Bacteria strains were spread on the surface of the nutrient agar, while the fungal isolates were spread on the potato dextrose agar using the sterile cotton swab. The recommended concentration of the test sample in DMSO was introduced in the respective wells. Other well

supplemented with the standard antibacterial drug and antifungal drug; i.e. (Gentamycin and Nystatin) respectively, to served as positive controls. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24h in the case of bacteria and 37°C for 48h in the case of fungi. The activity was determined by measuring the diameter of zones showing complete inhibition in (mm) (Neelofar *et al.*, 2017).

Results Discussion:

Table 1: Physical and Analytical Data of Schiff base and its metal Complexes

Compound	Color	Mol. Formula	Mol.wt	Melt.pt/Dec. Temp.(°C)	%Yield	Elemental analysis Calculate (Found)		
						%C	%H	%N
Schiff base	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ NCIO	218.5	123	82.40	72.47 (72.22)	4.26 (6.02)	4.97 (6.12)
[FeL ₂]	Green	C ₃₄ H ₂₂ FeN ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	616.9	223	72.56	66.14 (67.09)	3.57 (3.98)	4.54 (4.83)
[MnL ₂]	Brown	C ₃₄ H ₂₂ MnN ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	615.9	201	84.42	66.24 (66.53)	3.57 (3.68)	4.55 (5.69)

Key: L = Ligand

Table 2: Solubility of the Schiff base and the Complexes in some common Solvents

Compound	Water	Methanol	Ethanol	Chloroform	Acetone	DMF	DMSO
Schiff base	IS	S	S	S	S	S	S
[FeL ₂]	IS	S	S	S	S	S	S
[MnL ₂]	IS	S	S	S	S	S	S

L = Ligand, DMSO = Dimethylsulfoxide, DMF = Dimethylformamide, IS = Insoluble, SS = Slightly soluble, S = Soluble

Table 3: IR Spectra of the Schiff base and metal Complexes

Compound	V(C=N) cm ⁻¹	V(M-O) cm ⁻¹	V(M-N) cm ⁻¹	V(H ₂ O) cm ⁻¹
Schiff base	1607	-	-	-
[FeL ₂]	1618	605	501	-
[MnL ₂]	1603	618	511	-

Key: L= Ligand

Table 4: Conductivity Measurement of Complexes in DMSO

Complex	Concentration Mol dm ⁻³	Specific Conductance Ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Molar Conductance Ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
[FeL ₂]	1.0×10 ⁻³	5.83×10 ⁻⁶	5.83
[MnL ₂]	1.0×10 ⁻³	3.54×10 ⁻⁶	3.54

Key: L= Ligand, DMSO= Dimethylsulfoxide

Table 5: Magnetic Susceptibility of the Complexes

Compound	X _g (gmol ⁻¹)	X _m (gmol ⁻¹)	μ _{eff} (BM)	Property
[FeL ₂]	1.93×10 ⁻⁵	1.19×10 ⁻²	5.33	Paramagnetic
[MnL ₂]	2.52×10 ⁻⁵	1.55×10 ⁻²	6.08	Paramagnetic

Key: L = Ligand

Table 6a: Antibacterial activity of Schiff base and its metal Complexes

Compound	Diameter of inhibition zone(mm)/concentration						
	S.Typhi			S.pneumoniae			Control
	15µg	30µg	60µg	15µg	30µg	60µg	30µg
Schiff base	8	9	11	7	8	11	Gentamycin
[FeL ₂]	12	14	17	9	13	15	31
[MnL ₂].	11	15	18	9	14	16	

Key: S = Salmonella and streptococcus, L = Ligand

Table 6b: Antifungal activity of Schiff base and its metal Complexes

Compound	Diameter of inhibition zone(mm)/concentration						
	A.Fumigatus			R.species			Control
	15µg	30µg	60µg	15µg	30µg	60µg	30µg
Schiff base	7	8	10	7	9	11	Nystatin
[FeL ₂]	8	10	11	9	10	12	38
[MnL ₂].	8	10	13	9	12	15	

Key: A = Aspergillus, R = Rhizopus, L = Ligand

Discussion:

The reaction between 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and p-chloroaniline yielded Schiff base ligand (N-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-p-chloroaniline) which is yellow solid with a percentage yield of 82.40% and a melting point of 123°C. (Table 1) this is in agreement with the color and closer to the melting point reported by Gomathi *et al.*, (2013). The elemental analysis data revealed slight differences between the calculated and observed percentage values of CHN respectively (Table 1).

The interaction between the Schiff base ligand and a hydrated metal salt of Fe(II) and Mn(II) formed complexes with different colors (Table 1) the colors may be due to charge transfer or the nature of the ligand. The decomposition temperature Complexes fall in the range of 201°C-223°C respectively (Table 1), these temperatures are relatively high indicating the good stability of the Complexes due to the formation of large rings, and this is closer to the results reported by (Uddin *et al.*, 2014). Also, the elemental analysis data revealed slight differences between the calculated and observed percentage values of CHN respectively (Table 1). These values are in good agreement with the proposed structures of the prepared complexes.

The Schiff base and its metal complexes are soluble in some common organic solvents such as methanol, acetone, chloroform, Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), and Dimethylformamide (DMF), and slightly soluble in ethanol and insoluble in water. (Table 2)

The values obtained in the spectrum of the Schiff base showed a band at 1607cm⁻¹ which is attributed to V (>C=N-) stretching vibration and this band shifted to another region 1618cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the Fe(II) complex and 1603cm⁻¹ region in the spectrum of the Mn(II) complex. (Table 3) indicating the coordination of the Schiff base ligand to the metal ion through the nitrogen atom of the azomethine group. The new bands appeared in the spectra of the Fe(II) and Mn(II) complexes at 605-618cm⁻¹ and 501-511cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to V(M-O) and V(M-N) stretching vibration respectively, (Table 3) also indicating the coordination of the Schiff base ligand to the metal(II) ion.

Figure 1: Spectrum of Schiff base

Figure 2: Spectrum of Fe(II) Complex

Figure 3: Spectrum of Mn(II) Complex

The molar conductance value obtained in (Table 4) range $3.54\text{-}5.83\text{Ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$ indicated the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The values obtained are very close to the values reported in the previous literature. The values obtained from magnetic susceptibility measurement of all the complexes at room temperature shows values; 5.33BM for Fe(II) complex and 6.08BM for Mn(II) complex, and these values indicated the paramagnetic nature of the complexes (Table 5).

The antimicrobial activity of the Schiff base ligand and its metal complexes was conducted using the agar well diffusion method against two bacterial strains (*Salmonella typhi* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*) and two fungal isolates (*Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Rhizopus species*). The diameter of the inhibition zones was measured and recorded as shown in Table 6a & 6b. The results showed that the Schiff base ligand and its metal complexes exhibit promising antimicrobial activity against the tested organism, the Gentamycin and Nystatin were used as standards respectively. The activity of the Schiff base ligand and its metal complexes increase by increasing concentration, And also the metal complexes showed higher activity than free ligand due to the chelation processes which shows rises in the lipophilicity of the metal complexes by increasing the delocalization of π electron over full chelates ring. The improved lipophilicity helps the metal complex to penetrate into the lipid membrane and block the metal-binding sites of enzymes of the microorganism, and this affects the protein synthesis and further growth of the organism by inhibiting the respiration process of the cell. Similar reported by (Matangi *et al.*, 2013)

Conclusion:

The Schiff base derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and p-chloroaniline and its corresponding Fe(II) and Mn(II) complexes were synthesized and characterized successfully. The complexes are non-electrolytic and paramagnetic in nature, other analytical data revealed 1:2 metal-ligand ratios in all the complexes. The Schiff base and its metal complexes are soluble in some organic solvents such as Methanol, Acetone, DMSO and DMF etc. Both the Schiff base ligand and its metal complexes indicated promising antimicrobial activity.

Figure 4: Propose structure of the prepared metal complexes

References:

- Aliyu, H. N. and Ado, I. (2011). Studies of Mn(II) and Ni(II) Complexes with Schiff base derived from 2-amino benzoic acid and Salicylaldehyde. *Journal of biokemistri*, 23(1): 1-22
- Anita, B., Dominick, C., Tomislav, F., Branko, K. and Vladimir, S. (2010). Schiff bases derived from hydroxyaryl aldehyde: molecular and crystal structure, tautomerism, quinoid effect, coordination compounds, *Macedonian journal of chemistry and chemical engineering*. Vol. 29, No. 2, pp. 117–138
- Bharat, A. M., Pratik, N. D. and Pratik, B. T. (2015). Synthesis of Schiff bases and their transition metal complexes characterization & application, *International Journal of Science, Technology*. 04 (01), Pp. 118-123
- Chaudhary, N.K. (2013). Synthesis and medicinal use of Metal Complexes of Schiff bases, *a multidisciplinary Journal of Science, Technology and Mathematics*.9 (1), pp.75-80.
- Gomathi, V., Selvameena, R., Subbalakshmi, R. and Valak, M. (2013). Synthesis, spectral characterization and antimicrobial screening of Mn(II) and Zn(II) complexes derived from (E)-1-((P-tolylimino)methyl)naphthalene-2-ol) *Oriental Journal of Chemistry and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 29(2), pp. 533 – 538

- Ibrahim, A. K., Yusuf, B. A. and Hamisu, A. (2017). Synthesis, Characterization and Antimicrobial Studies of Cu(II) and Zn(II) Complexes with the Schiff base N-salicylidene-4-chloroaniline, *Chemsearch Journal*, 8(2): 68 – 74.
- Iniama, G. E. Isaac, T. I. (2013). Synthesis, Characterization and Antimicrobial Studies of Mn(II) Co(II) and Zn(II) Schiff base Complexes Derived from L-Arginine and 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthaldehyde, *International Journal of Science and Research* 4(6), pp. 979 - 982.
- Jai, D., Suman, D. and Ashwani, K. (2016). Synthesis, antibacterial evaluation and QSAR analysis of Schiff base complexes derived from [2,2'-(ethylenedioxy)bis(ethylamine)] and aromatic aldehyde, *Journal of Royal Society of Chemistry*, (7), pp. 932- 946
- Javed, I. (2006). Biological properties of Chloro-salicylidene Amine and Complexes with Co(II) and Cu (II). *Turk. Journal of Biochemistry*, 30(1):1-4
- Matangi, S., Pragathi, J., Ushaiah and Gyanakumari, C. (2012). Synthesis, structural characterization, molecular modeling and antimicrobial studies of transition metal complexes of Schiff base ligand derived from 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde and 2-(2-aminophenyl) 1H benzimidazole, *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 2012, 4(3), pp. 1553-1561
- Moamens, R. and Ibrahim, M. (2013). Spectroscopic, Structural and Electrical Conductivity studies of Cu(II), Ni(II) and C(II) Complexes derived from 4-acetylpyridine with thiosemicarbazide. *International journal of Electrochemical Science*. 1(8), pp. 9898-9917.
- Muzammil, K., Trivedi, P. and Khetani, D. B. (2015). Synthesis and characterization of Schiff base m-nitro aniline and their complexes, *Research Journal of Chemical Sciences*, 5 (5), pp. 52-55.
- Neelofar, N. A., Adnan K., Salma, A., Noureen, A. K. and Muhammad, B. (2017). Synthesis of Schiff bases derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, and their Tin(II) complexes for antimicrobial and antioxidant activities, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Ethiop.* 2017, 31 (3), pp. 445-456.
- Rajendra, A. P., Mishra, A. T. and Gupta S. K. (2012). Microwave synthesis, spectral, thermal and antimicrobial activities of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) Schiff base metal complexes, *Research Article-018*, 12 (2), pp. 112-118
- Uddin, M. N., Salam, M. A., Chowdhury, D. A., Sultana, J. and Halim, M. E. (2014). Trigonal Pyramidal Pb (II) Complexes of Schiff bases of Orthoaminophenol: Synthesis, Characterization and Antibacterial Evaluation. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Chemical Science* 1(6), pp. 47-56
- Yusuf, B. A., Ibrahim, A. K. and Hamisu, A. (2018). Synthesis, Physico-chemical and antimicrobial evaluation of Cu(II), Fe(II), Mn(II) Complexes with Schiff base derived from sulphanilamine and salicylaldehyde, *Chemsearch Journal*, 9(1): pp. 1-8, June